

A New Synthesis of ($\pm$)-Pulegone

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A new synthesis of ($\pm$)-pulegone employing Kochetkov's procedure has been described.

As a part of our study towards the synthesis of terpenes from appropriate cyclic diketones¹ as key intermediates, we have accomplished another synthesis of ($\pm$)-pulegone from a suitable β -exocyclic diketone. The present synthesis, unlike the earlier approaches^{2,3}, employs Kochetkov's procedure⁴ whereby the carbonyl group in the ring is protected selectively as dioxolane derivative while the keto-group in the side chain may be submitted to the Grignard reaction,

2-(*N*-Pyrrolidyl)-4-methylcyclohex-1-one (II) was obtained from 3-methylcyclohexanone under the conditions prescribed by Stork *et al.*⁵

1. Vig *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 432; 1958, **35**, 715; Gandhi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 200.

2. Mukherji *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1950, **33**, 853.

3. Black *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2971.

4. *J. Gen. Chem., USSR*, 1960, **30**, 2275.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 284; 1963, **85**, 2178; Siegfried and Wilhelum, *Chem. Ber.*, 1960, **93**, 909.

The structure of the compound (II) was established through pilot experiments involving its methylation:

The identity of the ketone (IIA) was established⁶ *via* its semicarbazone derivative, m.p. 121°.

Compound (II) was acylated with acetyl chloride in chloroform to furnish 1-acetyl-2-(*N*-pyrrolidyl)-4-methylcyclohex-1-ene (which was not isolated), which on subsequent hydrolysis provided 2-acetyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (III) in 64.5% yield. Ketone (III) was ketalised⁷ with ethylene glycol in refluxing benzene to afford 2-acetyl-5-methylcyclohexanone-1-dioxolane (IV) in 62.2% yield. The mono-ketal (IV) was then treated with methylmagnesium iodide to furnish (4-methyl-2-keto-2-dioxolane)-cyclohexyldimethyl carbinol (V) in 90% yield. Subsequent protonic hydrolysis of the ketal-carbinol (VI) yielded 2-keto-4-methylcyclohexyldimethyl carbinol (not isolated), which on distillation with a grain of iodine⁸ afforded 5-methyl-2-isopropylidenecyclohexanone (I) in 75% yield.

Compound (I) showed UV absorption maximum at 253 m μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.745) in agreement with the value $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 253 m μ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.84), recorded by Naves and Papazian⁹ for natural pulegone.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2-(*N*-Pyrrolidyl)-4-methylcyclohex-1-ene (II).—A mixture of 3-methylcyclohexanone (37.3 g.), pyrrolidine (33.2 g.), and dry benzene (200 ml) was refluxed in an oil bath (120°) in a Dean and Stark apparatus. After removal of the solvent the enamine (II) distilled at 104°/5mm; yield 46.7g. (85%), n_D^{20} 1.4915. (Found: C, 79.80; H, 11.42; N, 8.30. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₉N: C, 80.00; H, 11.51; N, 8.48%).

2,5-Dimethylcyclohexanone (IIA).—A mixture of the enamine (II) (10 g.), methyl iodide (8.05 g.), and methanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 10 hr. Methanol was expelled under diminished pressure and the residue after addition of water (20 ml) was stirred for 2 hr. at the room temperature. The oil was separated and the aqueous phase extracted thrice with ether. The residue, obtained after removal of the solvent from the combined extract, was distilled under 27mm pressure, when the ketone (IIA) came over at 76-77°; yield 5.65 g. (74%).

*The melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

6. Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. II, 1953, p. 294, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London.

7. Cf. Salmi, *Ber.*, 1939, 71B, 1803.

8. Cf. Stauffacher and Schinz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 1239.

The semicarbazone of (IIA) was crystallised from ethanol in colorless leaflets, m.p. 121° (lit.⁶ m.p. 122°).

2-Acetyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (III).—To a solution of (II) (25 g.) and triethylamine (16.2 g.) in dry chloroform (150 ml) was introduced dropwise acetyl chloride (12.16 g.) in dry chloroform (50 ml) in cold. After keeping overnight, the reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hr. with HCl (conc., 20 ml) and boiling water (50 ml). The reaction mixture was extracted with ether ($\times 4$). The residual oil, obtained after removing the solvent from the acid-free combined ethereal extracts, provided the pure compound, b.p. 95-100°/7mm, yield 15 g. (64.5%), n_D^{27} 1.4510. (Found: C, 70.30; H, 9.25. Calc. for $C_9H_{14}O_2$: C, 70.10; H, 9.15%.)

2-Acetyl-5-methylcyclohexanone-1-dioxolane (IV).—Compound (III) (15 g.), ethylene glycol (7.5 g.), dry benzene (150 ml), and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (50 mg.) were refluxed in an oil bath (120°) in a Dean and Stark apparatus. The reaction mixture after neutralising with sodium ethoxide was diluted sufficiently with water, worked up in the usual way, and distilled; the ketal (IV) came over at 115°/4mm, yield 12 g. (62.2%), n_D^{27} 1.4660. (Found: C, 66.20; H, 9.30. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$: C, 66.64; H, 9.15%.)

(4-Methyl-2-keto-2-dioxolane)-cyclohexyldimethyl Carbinol (V).—To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (1.2 g.) and methyl iodide (8 g.) in dry ether (100 ml), was added dropwise a solution of the above ketal (IV, 15 g.) in dry ether (50 ml) in the cold. After keeping the reaction mixture overnight, it was decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner when the carbinol (V) was obtained; b.p. 132-35°/7mm, yield 11.6 g. (90%), n_D^{20} 1.4662. (Found: C, 66.97; H, 10.42. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$: C, 67.25; H, 10.28%.)

5-Methyl-2-isopropylidencyclohexanone (I).—The preceding carbinol (8.5 g.) was refluxed for an hour with diluted ethanol (10 ml in 100 ml water) and two drops of HCl (conc.). It was then diluted with water and extracted with ether ($\times 3$). The residue after removing the solvent from the combined extracts was distilled under reduced pressure with a crystal of iodine, providing 4.5 g. (75%) of ($\pm$)-pulegone (I); b.p. 101-103°/10mm, n_D^{20} 1.4845 (lit.² records b.p. 84°/6 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4846); $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 253 m μ (log ϵ , 3.745); Naves and Papazian² record $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 253 m μ (log ϵ , 3.84). (Found: C, 78.67; H, 10.43. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%.)

The 2,4- DNP, prepared by the sulphuric acid method in the cold, was crystallised from ethyl acetate as bright red needles, m.p. 142° (lit.² m.p. 142°). (Found: N, 16.7. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 16.86%.)

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner without heating the reaction mixture. On crystallisation from ethanol it melted at 169-70° (lit.² m.p. 172°). (Found: N, 20.02. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{19}ON_3$: N, 20.08%.)